

ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE QUANTITATIVE ESTIMATION OF SAROGLITAZAR IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORMS BY USING RP-HPLC

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ABSTRACT

Objective: A rapid, sensitive, selective, and reproducible reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatographic method has been developed and validated for the determination of Saroglitazar (BRG), is an anaplastic lymphoma kinase inhibitor used to treat anaplastic lymphoma kinase positive metastatic non-small cell lung cancer. **Methods:** The chromatographic separation was carried out in an isocratic mode on a Phenomenex Luna C18, 100A, 5 μ m, 250mm x 4.6mm i.d. column with a mobile phase consisting of methanol and acetonitrile containing in the ratio of 80:20% v/v at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. The run time was maintained for 8.0 min and detection was monitored at 271 nm. **Results:** The calibration plot was linear over the concentration range of 6–16 μ g mL⁻¹ with limits of detection and quantification values of 0.5 and 0.15ng mL⁻¹ respectively. The mean % assay of marketed formulation was found to be 99.85%, and % recovery was observed in the range of 98-102%. Relative standard

deviation for the precision study was found <2%. **Conclusion:** This method was found to be simple, selective, precise, accurate, and cost-effective. Hence, the method can be successfully applied to analyze the Saroglitazar in bulk form and marketed pharmaceutical dosage forms.

KEYWORDS: Saroglitazar, RP-HPLC, Method Development, Validation, Precision.

INTRODUCTION

Saroglitazar is a monocarboxylic acid that is (2S)-2-ethoxy-3-(p-ethoxy phenyl) propanoic acid in which one of the methyl hydrogens of the p-ethoxy substituent has been replaced by the nitrogen of 2-methyl-5-[4-(methylthio) phenyl]-1H-pyrrole. An agonist at the subtypes alpha and gamma of the peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPAR) with predominant PPARalpha activity, it is used in the treatment of type 2 diabetes. It has a role as a PPARgamma agonist, a hypoglycemic agent and a PPARalpha agonist. It is a member of pyrroles, a monocarboxylic acid, a methyl sulfide and aromatic ether. Saroglitazar is a drug that is used to reduce triglycerides and cholesterol levels in people who have type 2 diabetes who have high lipid levels that aren't regulated by statin therapy. The drug is useful for the treatment of hypertriglyceridemia and controls high blood sugar and blood glucose. The IUPAC Name of Saroglitazar is (2S)-2-ethoxy-3-[4-[2-[2-methyl-5-(4-methyl sulfanyl phenyl) pyrrol-1-yl] ethoxy] phenyl] propanoic acid and Chemical Structure of Saroglitazar is shown in following figure-1.

Fig. 1: Chemical Structure of Saroglitazar.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Saroglitazar working Standard & Reference standards were obtained as gift samples from Aarti Drugs Ltd. Mumbai. HPLC grade acetonitrile and methanol, Water was purchased from

Sigma Aldrich chemicals, Mumbai, India. Analytical Grade Orthophosphoric Acid and Ammonium Acetate were purchased from SD fine chemicals, Mumbai, India.

Chromatographic Conditions

The HPLC system consisted of HPLC with Empower2 Software with Isocratic with UV-Visible Detector (Waters). The wavelength of detection as set at 271nm. Separation was carried out on Phenomenex Luna C18, 100A, 5 μ m, and 250mm x 4.6mm i.d. column using Methanol and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 35:65% v/v as mobile phase with isocratic elution at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. Retention time of Saroglitazar found to be 3.417min. The mobile phase filtered through nylon milli pore (0.2 μ m) membrane filter, purchased from pall life sciences, Mumbai and degassed with Ultrasonicator prior to use.^[1-3] Chromatography was carried out at room temperature and the column temperature at was ambient.

Preparation of Mobile Phase

650mL (65%) of Acetonitrile and 350mL of Methanol (35%) were mixed well and degassed in ultrasonic water bath for 15 minutes. The solution was filtered through 0.45 μ m filter under vacuum filtration.^[4]

Sample & Standard Preparation for the Analysis

25 mg of Saroglitazar standard was transferred into 25 ml volumetric flask, dissolved & make up to volume with mobile phase. Further dilution was done by transferring 0.4ml of the above solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and make up to volume with mobile phase.

Optimization of Chromatographic Conditions

The chromatographic conditions were optimized by different means. (Using different column, different mobile phase, different flow rate, different detection wavelength & different diluents for sample preparation etc.^[5-8]

Table 1: Summary of Process Optimization.

Column Used	Mobile Phase	Flow Rate	Wave length	Observation	Result
Phenomenex Luna C ₁₈ , 100A, 5 μ m, 250mmx4.6mm i.d.	Methanol : Water = 75:25	1.0ml/min	271nm	Very Low response	Method rejected
Phenomenex Luna C ₁₈ , 100A, 5 μ m, 250mmx4.6mm i.d.	Methanol : Water = 50:50	1.0ml/min	271nm	Low response	Method rejected
Phenomenex Luna	Acetonitrile: Water	1.0ml/min	271nm	Tailing	Method

C ₁₈ , 100A, 5µm, 250mmx4.6mm i.d.	= 60:40			peaks	rejected
Phenomenex Luna C ₁₈ , 100A, 5µm, 250mmx4.6mm i.d.	Methanol :Acetonitrile=50:50	1.0ml/ min	271nm	Broad Peak	Method rejected
Phenomenex Luna C ₁₈ , 100A, 5µm, 250mmx4.6mm i.d.	Methanol :Acetonitrile =80:20	1.0ml/ min	271nm	Tailing peaks	Method rejected
Phenomenex Luna C ₁₈ , 100A, 5µm, 250mmx4.6mm i.d.	Acetonitrile: Methanol =65:35	1.0ml/ min	271nm	Good Peak	Method accepted

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Selection of Wavelength

The standard & sample stock solutions were prepared separately by dissolving standard & sample in a solvent in mobile phase diluting with the same solvent. (After optimization of all conditions) for UV analysis. It is scanned in the UV spectrum in the range of 200 to 400nm.

This has been performed to know the maxima of Saroglitazar, so that the same wave number can be utilized in HPLC UV detector for estimating the Saroglitazar.^[9] While scanning the Saroglitazar solution we observed the maxima at 271 nm. The UV spectrum has been recorded on ELICO SL-159 make UV – Vis spectrophotometer model UV-2450. The scanned UV spectrum is shown below.

Fig. 2: UV Spectrum for Saroglitazar (271 nm).

Analytical Method Development

Summary of Optimized Chromatographic Conditions: The Optimum Chromatographic conditions obtained from experiments can be summarized as below^[10-12].

Table 2: Summary of Optimized Chromatographic Conditions.

Mobile phase	Methanol :Acetonitrile = 35:65% v/v
Column	Phenomenex Luna C ₁₈ , 100A, 5 μ m, 250mmx4.6mm i.d.
Flow rate	1.0 ml/ min.
Wavelength	271nm
Sampling System	Automatic
Temp. of Auto sampler	Ambient
Volume of Injection	10 μ l
Run time	08 min.
Mode of Separation	Isocratic

Fig. 3: Chromatogram of Saroglitazar in Optimized Condition.

Validation of Analytical Method

The developed chromatographic method was validated for Specificity, Linearity, Precision, Accuracy, Sensitivity, Robustness and System suitability.^[13-16]

Linearity and Range: Standard solutions of Saroglitazar in the concentration range of 0 μ g/ml to 16 μ g/ml were obtained by transferring (0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6ml) of Saroglitazar stock solution (1000ppm) to the series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. The volumetric flasks were made up to the mark with mobile phase. The solutions were filtered through a 0.45 μ m membrane filter and degassed under ultrasonic bath. The final resulted solutions were injected into HPLC the system. The run time/stop time maintained was 8 min and the various types of peak areas were measured.^[17] The calibration data are shown in Table 3 and calibration curve data are shown in figure-4.

Table 3: Calibration Data for Saroglitazar.

S. No.	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Mean Peak Area
1	0	0
2	6	61233
3	8	84610
4	10	110247
5	12	130435
6	14	153354
7	16	172043

Fig. 4: Calibration Curve for Saroglitazar.**Accuracy: Recovery Study of Saroglitazar**

The accuracy of the proposed developed method the % recovery studies were carried out by adding different quantities (80%, 100%, and 120%) of pure drug of Saroglitazar was taken and added to the prepared pre-analyzed formulation of concentration $10\mu\text{g/ml}$. From that % recovery values were measured.^[18] The results were shown in Table-4.

Table 4: Data of Recovery Studies for Saroglitazar.

Sample ID	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)		Peak Area	% Recovery of Pure drug	Statistical Analysis
	Amount Added	Amount Found			
S ₁ : 80 %	8	8.105	93435	101.312	Mean= 100.0163% S.D. = 1.293505 % R.S.D.= 1.293294
S ₂ : 80 %	8	7.898	91287	98.725	
S ₃ : 80 %	8	8.001	92356	100.012	
S ₄ : 100 %	10	10.195	115135	101.95	Mean= 101.4033% S.D. = 0.613379 % R.S.D.= 0.60489
S ₅ : 100 %	10	10.152	114687	101.52	
S ₆ : 100 %	10	10.074	113879	100.74	
S ₇ : 120 %	12	12.171	135647	101.425	Mean= 100.6053% S.D. = 0.730041 % R.S.D. = 0.725649
S ₈ : 120 %	12	12.044	134324	100.366	
S ₉ : 120 %	12	12.003	133897	100.025	

Precision: Repeatability

Repeatability was assessed using six time repetition of working concentration.^[19] The results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Data Showing Repeatability Analysis for Saroglitazar.

HPLC Injection Replicates of Saroglitazar	Area Under the Curve
Replicate – 1	112546
Replicate – 2	113824
Replicate – 3	111351
Replicate – 4	111584
Replicate – 5	112419
Replicate – 6	112572
Average	112382
Standard Deviation	876.7543
% RSD	0.7801

Intermediate Precision**Intra-Assay & Inter-Assay**

The intra & inter day variation of the method was carried out & the high values of mean assay & low values of standard deviation & % RSD (% RSD < 2%) within a day & day to day variations for Saroglitazar revealed that the proposed method is precise.^[20]

Table 6: Results of Intra-Assay & Inter-Assay for Saroglitazar.

Conc. of Saroglitazar (API) (µg/ml)	Observed Conc. of Saroglitazar (µg/ml) by the Proposed Method			
	Intra-Day		Inter-Day	
	Mean (n=6)	% RSD	Mean (n=6)	% RSD
8	8.07	0.27	8.95	0.34
10	10.39	0.39	10.56	0.65
12	11.19	0.23	12.01	0.34

Method Robustness

The influence of small changes in optimized chromatographic conditions such as changes in Flow Rate (± 0.1 ml/min), Organic Phase ($\pm 5^{\circ}$ C), Wavelength of detection (± 2 nm) & Mobile Phase ($\pm 2\%$) studied to determine the robustness of the method are also in favour of (Table-7, RSD (%) < 2%) the proposed RP-HPLC method was used for the analysis of Saroglitazar (API).^[21]

Table 7: Result of Method Robustness Test.

Change in Parameter	% RSD
Flow (1.1 ml/min)	1.13
Flow (0.9 ml/min)	0.09
More Organic	0.78
Less Organic	0.72
Wavelength of Detection (273 nm)	0.77
Wavelength of detection (269 nm)	0.59

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification

The limit of detection and limit of quantization (LOD and LOQ) can be determined by the following equations. These equations are based on the signal to noise ratio. These two equations are useful for the determination of LOD and LOQ.

$$\text{L.O.D.} = 3.3 (\text{SD/S}) \ \& \ \text{L.O.Q.} = 10 (\text{SD/S})$$

Where,

SD = Standard deviation Response

S = Slope of the Calibration curve

Observation: The LOD was found to be 0.05 µg/ml and LOQ was found to be 0.15 µg/ml for Saroglitazar which represents that sensitivity of the method is high.^[22]

System Suitability Parameter

This includes the type of equipment, electronics, analytical operations and samples to be analyzed constitute an integral system that can be examined. The following system suitability test parameters were determined.^[23] The obtained data are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Data of System Suitability Parameter.

S.No.	Parameter	Limit	Result
1	Resolution	$R_s > 2$	6.81
2	Asymmetry	$T \leq 2$	Saroglitazar = 0.26
3	Theoretical plate	$N > 2000$	Saroglitazar = 6986

Assay of Saroglitazar in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form

Twenty pharmaceutical dosage forms were taken and the I.P. method was followed to determine the average weight. Above weighed tablets were finally powdered and triturated well. A quantity of powder equivalent to 100 mg of drugs were transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask, and 70 ml of mobile phase was added and solution was sonicated for 15 minutes, there after volume was made up to 100 ml with same solvent. Then 10 ml of the

above solution was diluted to 100 ml with HPLC grade methanol. The solution was filtered through a membrane filter (0.45 µm) and sonicated to degas. From this stock solution (1.0ml) was transferred to five different 10 ml volumetric flasks and volume was made up to 10 ml with same solvent system.^[24-26] The solution prepared was injected in five replicates into the HPLC system and the observations were recorded. A duplicate injection of the standard solution was also injected into the HPLC system and the peak areas were recorded.

Assay % =

$$\frac{\text{AT} \times \text{WS} \times \text{DT} \times \text{P}}{\text{AS} \times \text{WT} \times 100} \times \text{Avg. Wt} = \text{mg/tab}$$

Where:

AT = Peak Area of Test obtained with test preparation

AS = Peak Area of Standard obtained with standard preparation

WS = Weight of working standard taken in mg

WT = Weight of sample taken in mg

DS = Dilution of Standard solution

DT = Dilution of sample solution

P = Percentage purity of working standard

Assay was performed as described in previous chapter. Results obtained are tabulated below:

Table 9: Assay of Saroglitazar Tablets.

Brand Name of Tablets	Labelled Amount of Drug (mg)	Mean (± SD) Amount (mg) Found by the Proposed Method (n=6)	Mean (± SD) Assay (n = 6)
Lipaglyn Tablet (Zydus Health Care Ltd.)	4mg	3.749 (± 0.587)	99.968 (± 0.748)

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

To develop a precise, linear, specific & suitable stability indicating RP-HPLC method for simultaneous analysis of Saroglitazar different chromatographic conditions were applied & the results observed are presented in previous chapters. Isocratic elution is simple, requires only one pump & flat baseline separation for easy and reproducible results. So, it was preferred for the current study over gradient elution. In case of RP-HPLC various columns

are available, but here Phenomenex Luna C₁₈, 100A, 5 μ m, 250mm x 4.6mm i.d. column was preferred because using this column peak shape, resolution and absorbance were good. Detection wavelength was selected after scanning the standard solution of drug over 200 to 400nm. From the U.V spectrum of Saroglitazar it is evident that most of the HPLC work can be accomplished in the wavelength range of 271 nm conveniently. Further, a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min & an injection volume of 10 μ l were found to be the best analysis. The result shows the developed method is yet another suitable method for assay & stability which can help in the simultaneous analysis of Saroglitazar in different formulations.

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